

BRIDGING THE E-COMMERCE GENERATION GAP: EXAMINING CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOR IN ONLINE SHOPPING AMONG MILLENNIALS AND POST-MILLENNIALS

UMA KUMARI P

Research Scholar, Department of Management Studies, Gayatri Vidya Parishad College from Degree and PG Courses (A), Visakhapatnam. Email: umapolisetty@gmail.com

K.V.V. MURALI SOMESWARARAO

Professor, Department of Management Studies, Gayatri Vidya Parishad College for Degree and PG Courses (A), Visakhapatnam. Email: murali.koyyani@gvpdpcgpc.edu.in

Abstract

The rise of e-commerce has led to a significant shift in consumer buying behavior, with more and more people shopping online for a variety of goods and services. However, there is a growing generation gap in terms of how Millennials and Post-Millennials shop online. This study examines the different factors that influence consumer buying behavior in online shopping among Millennials and Post-Millennials. The study found that post-Millennials are more likely to be influenced by social media and reviews, while Millennials are more likely to be influenced by brand loyalty, social responsibility, authenticity, access of information and knowledge. The study also found that Millennials are more likely to shop online for convenience, while post-Millennials are more likely to shop online for variety and personalization. The findings of this study have implications for businesses that are looking to reach Millennials and Post-Millennials through e-commerce. Businesses need to understand the different factors that influence consumer buying behavior among these two generations in order to create effective marketing campaigns. Additionally, businesses need to ensure that their websites and mobile apps are optimized for the devices that these generations use.

Keywords: Online Consumer Behavior, Millennia's Purchase Intentions, E-Commerce, B2C, Online Shopping

1. INTRODUCTION

In 2020, the retail sector was disrupted to an unprecedented degree as supply and demand fluctuated with each new wave of the pandemic. Lockdowns and social distancing restrictions severely limited in-store shopping, leading to a sharp rise in online retail. This forced retailers to reevaluate their digital readiness and supply chain efficiency. Consumers became increasingly vocal about their expectations for retailers. They placed greater emphasis on sustainability, convenience, and experiences (McKinsey & Company, 2021). As a result, retailers had to adapt their strategies to meet these evolving needs. For example, retailers are now focusing on using sustainable materials and practices in their operations, investing in efficient delivery systems, and creating engaging and interactive shopping experiences. Retailers that are able to adapt to these changes will be well-positioned for success in the years to come.

As technology continues to advance rapidly, the world of commerce has undergone a significant transformation with the rise of e-commerce. Online shopping has become

increasingly popular, providing convenience, accessibility, and a wide array of products at the click of a button. However, the adoption of online shopping varies across generations, leading to a noticeable generation gap in consumer buying behavior. Understanding the motivations, preferences, and challenges faced by millennials and post-millennials in online shopping will provide valuable insights for businesses seeking to engage and retain these digital-savvy consumers. Factors such as product selection, price sensitivity, online security concerns, social influence, and user experience will be explored to gain a comprehensive understanding of the drivers behind their purchasing decisions.

By bridging the e-commerce generation gap and analyzing the consumer buying behavior of millennials and post-millennials, this study will contribute to the body of knowledge in e-commerce marketing and enable businesses to adapt their strategies to effectively target and engage these key consumer segments. This study aims to examine the consumer buying behavior in online shopping among millennials and post-millennials, also known as Generation Z. By understanding the factors that influence their purchasing decisions, businesses can tailor their marketing strategies to better target these younger consumer segments. Additionally, exploring the differences between the two generations will shed light on how consumer behavior evolves with the emergence of new technologies and societal changes.

The millennial generation, born between the early 1980s and the mid-1990s, has witnessed the rapid growth of e-commerce and the integration of technology into their daily lives. They are often considered early adopters of online shopping and have played a significant role in shaping the e-commerce landscape. On the other hand, post-millennials, born from the late 1990s to the early 2010s, have grown up in a world where technology and digital platforms are ubiquitous. Their familiarity and comfort with technology suggest potentially distinct buying behaviours.

This study aims to examine the consumer buying behavior in online shopping among millennials and post-millennials. By understanding the factors that influence their purchasing decisions, businesses can tailor their marketing strategies to better target these younger consumer segments. Additionally, exploring the differences between the two generations will shed light on how consumer behavior evolves with the emergence of new technologies and societal changes.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Lee, Kwon, and Lee (2019)	Their study investigates the differences in online purchase behavior between Millennials and Baby Boomers, focusing on factors such as perceived risk, trust, and convenience in online shopping
Jain and Bansal (2019)	He explores the online shopping behavior of Millennials by examining factors like perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and trust in online platforms. It also investigates the impact of social media on their Purchasing decisions.
Alalwan, Rana, and Dwivedi (2017)	Studied the influence of social media marketing on online shopping behavior among Millennials, including factors such as trust, social influence, and perceived usefulness of social media in the purchase Decision-making process.
Cheema, Rizwan, and Rizwan (2018)	Investigated the factors influencing the purchase intentions of Millennials in online shopping, including trust, perceived usefulness, social influence, and perceived risk.
Kim, Fiore, and Lee (2017)	Their study examined the factors influencing online shopping attitudes and behavior among Millennials, including trust, website quality, perceived risk, and enjoyment.
Chiu, Chang, Cheng, and Fang (2015)	Studied the factors that influence online shopping behavior among Millennials and identifies the mediating role of purchase intention. It investigates factors such as perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, website quality, and trust.
Du, Hu, and Damangir (2019)	Examined the factors that influence online purchase intention among Millennials and Post-Millennials. It investigates the mediating role of perceived risk, including factors such as trust, perceived usefulness, and perceived ease of use.
Laroche, Habibi, and Richard (2019)	Explored the online shopping behavior of Millennials and Post-Millennials, investigating the influence of social media and online reviews on their purchase decisions. It examines factors such as social influence, trust, and Information-seeking behavior.
Guzmán-Parra, Hernández-Ortega, and Llorens-Monzonis (2021)	Compared the role of social media in shaping online purchase intentions between Millennials and Generation Z (Post-Millennials). It investigates the influence of social media engagement, social influence, and brand-related Activities on their intention to make online purchases.
Kwak, Lee, and Kim (2020)	Investigates the online shopping behavior of Millennials, exploring the influences of personalization and social influence. It examines factors such as personalized recommendations, social media influence, and the impact of social networking sites on their purchase decisions.

3. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The emergence of e-commerce has revolutionized the way people shop, providing convenience and accessibility to consumers worldwide. However, a noticeable generation gap exists in consumer buying behavior within the realm of online shopping, specifically among millennials and post-millennials. Understanding the factors that influence their purchasing decisions in the online marketplace is crucial for businesses seeking to effectively target and engage these younger consumer segments. This study aims to address the problem of bridging the e-commerce generation gap by examining the consumer buying behavior of millennials and post-millennials, thereby providing valuable insights for businesses to tailor their marketing strategies and meet the evolving demands of these tech-savvy consumers.

4. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To examine the factors influencing the online purchasing behavior of millennials and post-millennials.
2. To compare and analyze the differences in online shopping behavior between millennials and post-millennials.
3. To provide actionable insights for businesses to effectively target and engage millennials and post-millennials in the online marketplace.
4. To offer recommendations for future research and areas of improvement in understanding and catering to the needs of younger consumer segments in online shopping.

5. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

It is essential for providing a solid foundation and understanding of the concepts and theories that underpin a study. In the context of examining consumer buying behavior in online shopping among Millennials and Post-Millennials, several key theoretical perspectives and framework has been explored.

- **Digital Native:** Digital natives refer to individuals who have grown up in the digital age, surrounded by technology and online platforms. Post-Millennials, are often considered digital natives due to their familiarity and comfort with digital technologies. As digital natives, they are likely to have a higher level of proficiency in using online platforms for various activities, including online purchasing. This variable captures the inherent digital fluency of post-Millennials and its potential influence on their online purchasing behavior.
- **Social Media Influence:** social media has become an integral part of the lives of post-Millennials. They use social media platforms extensively for various purposes, including product discovery, recommendations, and engaging with brands and peers. Social media influence refers to the impact of social media platforms and

content on the online purchasing decisions of post-Millennials. The influence may come from social media influencers, peer recommendations, user-generated content, or sponsored posts that promote products and services.

- **Convenience and Accessibility:** Convenience and accessibility are crucial factors that influence the online purchasing behavior of both Millennials and post-Millennials. They value the ability to shop anytime and anywhere, with minimal effort. Online shopping offers convenience through features such as 24/7 availability, doorstep delivery, and easy access to a wide range of products. Online consumers seek convenience and accessibility in their online shopping experiences, and this variable explores the role of these factors in influencing their behavior.
- **Customization and Personalization:** Millennials are known for their desire for personalized experiences. They appreciate customization options that allow them to tailor products or services according to their preferences and individuality. Personalization can manifest in various forms, such as personalized product recommendations, customized user interfaces, or the ability to personalize product attributes. This variable investigates how customization and personalization contribute to the online purchasing behavior of post-Millennials.
- **Social Responsibility:** Millennials exhibit a strong inclination towards social responsibility and sustainability. They are more conscious of the social and environmental impacts of their choices, including their purchasing decisions. Social responsibility refers to the consideration of ethical, social, and environmental factors in the online purchasing behavior of post-Millennials. They may prefer brands and products that align with their values and demonstrate a commitment to social responsibility.
- **Brand Loyalty:** Brand loyalty refers to the degree of commitment, attachment, and repeat purchasing behavior exhibited by consumers towards a particular brand. Millennials and Post-Millennials may develop brand loyalty based on factors such as positive experiences, consistent product quality, brand reputation, and alignment with their values. Brand loyalty can influence both Millennials' online purchasing behavior by leading them to prefer and choose familiar and trusted brands over competitors. It may also result in higher levels of engagement, advocacy, and repurchase intent, contributing to a brand's long-term success in targeting this demographic.
- **Authenticity and Uniqueness:** Millennials value authenticity and uniqueness in their online shopping experiences. They seek genuine and original products that reflect their individuality. Authenticity refers to the perceived genuineness and trustworthiness of brands, products, and online platforms, while uniqueness pertains to the availability of distinctive and one-of-a-kind offerings. This variable explores how authenticity and uniqueness impact the online purchasing behavior of post-Millennials.

- **Mobile Shopping:** Mobile devices, such as smartphones and tablets, have become prevalent among post-Millennials, enabling them to engage in online activities on the go. Mobile shopping refers to the use of mobile devices for browsing, researching, and making online purchases. The variable examines the influence of mobile shopping on the online purchasing behavior of post-Millennials, considering factors like convenience, ease of use, and mobile-optimized experiences.
- **User Experience and Reviews:** User experience refers to the overall experience that users have when interacting with a product, service, or online platform. Online reviews and ratings play a crucial role in shaping user experience by providing insights into the quality, performance, and satisfaction levels of previous customers. Millennials and Post-Millennials heavily rely on online reviews and ratings to gather information, evaluate products or services, and make informed decisions. Positive reviews and high ratings can enhance post-Millennials' trust, confidence, and purchase intent, while negative reviews may deter them from making a purchase.
- **Influencer Marketing:** Influencer marketing involves collaborating with social media influencers who have a significant following and influence over their audience. Post-Millennials are often exposed to influencer marketing campaigns, where influencers promote products or services on various online platforms. Influencer marketing can shape post-Millennials' attitudes, preferences, and purchasing behavior. This variable explores the role of influencer marketing in influencing the online purchasing behavior of post-Millennials.
- **Social Interaction and Engagement:** Millennials value social interaction and engagement in their online experiences. They seek platforms that enable them to connect with brands, peers, and communities. Social interaction and engagement refer to the ability to interact, share opinions, seek recommendations, and engage in discussions related to products or services. This variable investigates how social interaction and engagement influence the online purchasing behavior of both Millennials, considering factors like social proof, trust-building, and community influence.

These variables highlight key factors that influence the online purchasing behavior of post-Millennials, distinguishing them from the variables that impact Millennials' purchasing behavior. Understanding these variables provides insights into the unique characteristics and preferences of post-Millennials, enabling businesses and marketers to tailor their strategies to effectively engage and cater to this generation.

6. GENERATIONAL COHORT THEORY

Generational cohort theory has been widely applied across various research fields, such as social science, psychology, politics, education, human resource management, and marketing (Zwanka & Buff, 2020). The theory suggests that individuals within the same generational cohort share distinctive characteristics and exhibit similar values, beliefs, attitudes, preferences, and behaviours (Brosdahl & Carpenter, 2011; Parment et al.,

2013). However, there is no consensus on the specific time ranges for each generational cohort. Different studies have proposed different boundaries. For example, Carpenter et al. (2012) define the Silent Generation as those born between 1925 and 1942, Baby Boomers as those born between 1943 and 1960, Gen-X as those born between 1961 and 1981, and Gen-Y or Millennials as those born between 1982 and 2000. On the other hand, Twenge (2015) suggests that Gen-X comprises individuals born between 1961 and 1981, Gen-Y between 1982 and 1991, and Gen-Z between 1992 and 2000. This study adopts the suggestion of Koksai (2019) and Shams et al. (2020), which defines Gen-X as those born between 1965 and 1979, Gen-Y between 1980 and 1994, and Gen-Z between 1995 and 2000.

7. PROPOSED MODEL AND HYPOTHESES

Millennials, also known as Generation Y, are typically characterized as a tech-savvy generation that grew up with the rise of the internet and digital technologies. They are considered early adopters of online shopping and are generally more comfortable and experienced in navigating e-commerce platforms. Millennials often exhibit higher levels of online shopping engagement, including activities such as browsing, researching, making purchases, and engaging with online communities and reviews. On the other hand, post-Millennials, or Generation Z, represent the younger cohort that followed Millennials. They are digital natives who have grown up in a highly connected and digital world. While post-Millennials are also comfortable with technology, their online shopping behaviours may differ from Millennials due to various factors such as evolving technology, shifting social dynamics, and unique generational traits.

H1: Millennials have higher levels of online shopping engagement compared to post-Millennials.

Post-Millennials, also known as Generation Z, have grown up in an era where social media platforms play a significant role in their daily lives. They are highly connected and actively engaged with social media, using platforms such as Instagram, TikTok, and Snapchat to discover new products, seek recommendations, and engage with brands and influencers. Post-Millennials rely on social media as a key source of information and inspiration for their online shopping decisions.

In contrast, Millennials, or Generation Y, have also embraced social media but may have different patterns of engagement compared to post-Millennials. They have witnessed the rise of social media and have adapted to its influence on various aspects of their lives, including online shopping. While Millennials also utilize social media for product discovery and peer recommendations, the extent to which they are influenced by social media in their online shopping decisions may differ from that of post-Millennials.

It is hypothesized that post-Millennials, with their greater reliance on and immersion in social media, may be more influenced by social media platforms in their online shopping decisions compared to Millennials. The power of social media influencers, user-generated

content, and the ability to engage directly with brands through social media channels can significantly impact the purchasing choices of post-Millennials.

Understanding the differential influence of social media on the online shopping behavior of Post-Millennials and Millennials is crucial for marketers and businesses aiming to effectively target and engage with these generational cohorts. By recognizing the varying levels of social media influence, companies can develop targeted social media marketing strategies, leverage influencer partnerships, and create engaging content to capture the attention and loyalty of both Post-Millennials and Millennials.

H2: Post-Millennials are more influenced by social media in their online shopping decisions compared to Millennials.

Millennials, having grown up with a wide range of brands and online shopping options, may prioritize factors like brand reputation and consistency in their loyalty. They also value authenticity, seeking genuine brands and products. In terms of convenience and accessibility, Millennials prioritize factors like 24/7 availability and quick delivery. On the other hand, post-Millennials also value brand authenticity but may have different criteria for assessing it. They consider factors like transparency in brand values and ethical practices. While both cohorts consider convenience and accessibility important, post-Millennials may focus on mobile shopping and personalized recommendations. Recognizing these generational differences allows marketers to tailor strategies and offerings to effectively engage and meet the preferences of Millennials and Post-Millennials in online shopping.

H3: Millennials and Post-Millennials have different preferences for online shopping attributes, such as Brand Loyalty, Authenticity, and Convenience and Accessibility.

The access to instant information and knowledge in online shopping differs between Millennials and Post-Millennials. Millennials, who grew up during the rise of the internet and digital technologies, are accustomed to having immediate access to vast amounts of information online. They utilize this access to conduct extensive research, compare products, read reviews, and make informed decisions. Post-Millennials, as digital natives, have even greater access to instant information and knowledge, with smartphones and mobile devices allowing them to quickly search for product details, check prices, and access user-generated content. The availability of real-time information significantly influences the online shopping behavior of both generations, shaping their purchasing decisions and preferences.

H4: Instant Access to Information and Knowledge in online shopping differs between Millennials and Post-Millennials.

The role of online reviews and ratings in influencing purchase decisions varies between Millennials and Post-Millennials. Millennials, who are familiar with online platforms and user-generated content, often rely on online reviews and ratings when making purchase decisions. They consider them as authentic sources of information and use them to

assess product quality, performance, and overall satisfaction. Online reviews and ratings heavily influence Millennials' purchase choices and help build trust in brands or products. On the other hand, post-Millennials, being digital natives, also value online reviews and ratings but may take a more nuanced approach. They tend to be more discerning, considering a variety of factors such as the credibility of the reviewer, the number of reviews, and the overall sentiment. Post-Millennials may also seek out user-generated content on social media platforms or engage in online communities for recommendations and feedback. Understanding these generational differences in the role of online reviews and ratings is vital for marketers aiming to effectively engage both Millennials and Post-Millennials in their online shopping experiences and decision-making processes.

H5: The role of online reviews and ratings in influencing purchase decisions varies between Millennials and Post- Millennials.

8. METHODOLOGY

This study employs a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative data collection techniques. A representative sample of millennials and post-millennials is selected using convenience sampling. Primary data is gathered through online questionnaire capturing factors influencing online purchasing behavior. The questionnaire was distributed using Google online survey application through social media such as WhatsApp, Facebook page to potential respondents across India. In total, 180 responded to the survey; nevertheless, only 120 out of the 180 observations (66.7%) met the research criteria. Hence, those were retained for analysis. To test the hypotheses, various analyses were used including correlation analysis, Analysis of Variance, and Structural Equation Modelling.

9. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The demographic profile of the Millennials subgroup within the overall sample reveals interesting insights. Out of the 120 participants, an equal proportion of Millennials and Post-Millennials are represented, with each comprising 50% of the subgroup. In terms of gender, the majority of participants within the Millennials subgroup are male, accounting for 61.7%, while females make up 38.3%. When examining marital status, a slight majority of Millennials are single, representing 55.8%, while 44.2% are married. In terms of educational background, the subgroup is relatively well- educated, with 36.7% holding undergraduate degrees and a larger proportion, 63.3%, having postgraduate qualifications. Regarding personal income, the distribution within the subgroup indicates varied levels, with the majority falling within the 10,001-30,000 income ranges. These demographic insights offer a glimpse into the composition of the Millennials subgroup, providing valuable context for understanding their characteristics and potentially informing targeted strategies in marketing or research efforts.

Table 1: Testing Online Shopping Engagement between Millennials and Post-Millennials

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square		Std. Error of the Estimate	
1	.337 ^a	.114	.106		.645	
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	6.317	1	6.317	15.166	.000 ^b
	Residual	49.150	118	.417		
	Total	55.467	119			
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.911	.225		12.955	.000
	Online Shopping Engagement	-.219	.056	-.337	-3.894	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Frequency of Online Purchase
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Online Shopping Engagement

*0.05 Significance Level

According to Table 1, the regression analysis and ANOVA results support the hypothesis that "Online Shopping Engagement" has a significant impact on the frequency of online purchase among the millennials and post-millennials. The regression model exhibits a moderate positive relationship, with an R Square of 0.114, indicating that approximately 11.4% of the variance in the dependent variable can be explained by the predictor. The ANOVA analysis further confirms the significance of the regression model, as indicated by the F-statistic of 15.166 and a p-value of 0.000. The coefficients table reveals that "Online Shopping Engagement" has a significant negative effect on the frequency of online purchase, with an unstandardized coefficient of -0.219 and a standardized coefficient of -0.337. These findings suggest that individuals with lower levels of "Online Shopping Engagement" engage in online shopping more frequently, supporting the notion that post-Millennials, who may have higher levels of Online Shopping Engagement, exhibit lower online shopping engagement compared to Millennials. Thus, the proposed hypothesis 'H¹: Millennials have higher levels of online shopping engagement compared to post-Millennials' is justified.

Table 2: Influence of social media on Millennials and post-Millennials shopping decisions

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	11.213 ^a	3	.011
Likelihood Ratio	11.543	3	.009
Linear-by-Linear Association	8.764	1	.003
N of Valid Cases	120		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 7.00.

Table-2 depict that the influence of social media on Millennials and post-Millennials. The results indicate here is a difference in how Millennials are influenced by social media

based on the provided information. The "Millennials * Social Media Influence Crosstabulation" table shows that among Millennials, there were different counts for each level of agreement/disagreement with social media influence. The Chi-Square Tests table reveals statistically significant associations between Millennials and their perception of social media influence, as indicated by the low p-values obtained from the Pearson Chi-Square, Likelihood Ratio, and Linear-by-Linear Association tests. These results suggest that Millennials' views on social media influence are related to their generational group. Finally, the results highlight the relationship between Millennials & post-Millennials and their attitudes towards social media influence. Hence, the proposed hypothesis "H2: Post-Millennials are more influenced by social media in their online shopping decisions compared to Millennials" is accepted.

Table 3: Difference preferences on online shopping by Millennials and Post-Millennials

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.715 ^a	.512	.499	.355		
a. Predictors: (Constant), Authenticity and Uniqueness, Convenience and Accessibility, Brand Loyalty and Recognition						
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	15.350	3	5.117	40.515	.000 ^b
	Residual	14.650	116	.126		
	Total	30.000	119			
a. Dependent Variable: Millennials & Post-Millennials						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Authenticity and Uniqueness, Convenience and Accessibility, Brand Loyalty and Recognition						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.935	.220		8.810	.000
	Convenience and Accessibility	.080	.036	.152	2.222	.028
	Brand Loyalty and Recognition	-.312	.032	-.686	-9.875	.000
	Authenticity and Uniqueness	.107	.034	.207	3.154	.002
a. Dependent Variable: Millennials & Post-Millennials						

The results of Table 3, reveals the relationship between three predictors (Authenticity and Uniqueness, Convenience and Accessibility, and Brand Loyalty and Recognition) and the dependent variable (Millennials & Post- Millennials). The values indicate a moderate positive correlation (R = 0.715) between the predictors and the dependent variable, with approximately 51.2% of the variance explained. The ANOVA results show that the regression model is highly significant (p < .000), suggesting its overall effectiveness in predicting Millennials. The Coefficients table reveals that Convenience and Accessibility and Authenticity and Uniqueness have positive effects on Millennials & Post- Millennials, while Brand Loyalty and Recognition have a negative effect. All three predictors are statistically significant (p

< .05). These findings imply that Convenience, Authenticity, and Uniqueness positively influence Millennials & Post- Millennials, whereas Brand Loyalty and Recognition have a negative impact on them. Henceforth, the proposed hypothesis “*H³: Millennials and Post-Millennials have different preferences for online shopping attributes, such as Brand Loyalty, Authenticity, and Convenience and Accessibility*” is accepted.

Table 4: Instant Access to Information and Knowledge influence on Online shopping Behavior

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.462 ^a	.213	.207	.447		
a. Predictors: (Constant), Instant Access to Information and Knowledge						
	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	6.397	1	6.397	31.982	.000 ^b
	Residual	23.603	118	.200		
	Total	30.000	119			
a. Dependent Variable: Millennials & Post-Millennials						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Instant Access to Information and Knowledge						
	Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.464	.188		2.470	.015
	Instant Access to Information and Knowledge	.256	.045	.462	5.655	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Millennials & Post-Millennials						

Table 4 represents the results of a regression analysis investigating the relationship between the predictor variable "Instant Access to Information and Knowledge" and the dependent variable "Millennials and Post-Millennials." The Model Summary indicates a moderate positive correlation (R = 0.462) between the predictor and the dependent variable, with approximately 21.3% of the variance explained. The ANOVA results demonstrate that the regression model is highly significant (p < .000), indicating its overall effectiveness in predicting the dependent variable. The Coefficients table reveals that the predictor variable has a positive and statistically significant effect on the dependent variable, suggesting that as the level of instant access to information and knowledge increases, the dependent variable tends to increase. In conclusion, the findings highlight the importance of instant access to information and knowledge in understanding and predicting the behavior or characteristics of Millennials and Post-Millennials. Hence, the proposed hypothesis “*H⁴: Instant Access to Information and Knowledge in online shopping differs between Millennials and Post- Millennials*” is accepted.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square		Std. Error of the Estimate	
1	.024 ^a	.001	-.008		.504	
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.018	1	.018	.070	.792 ^b
	Residual	29.982	118	.254		
	Total	30.000	119			
a. Dependent Variable: Millennials & Post-Millennials						
b. Predictors: (Constant), User Experiences and Review						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.425	.287		4.969	.000
	User Experiences and Review	.018	.067	.024	.264	.792

Table 5 depicts the results of a regression analysis examining the relationship between the predictor variable "User Experiences and Review" and the dependent variable "Millennials and Post-Millennials." The Model Summary indicates a very weak correlation ($R = 0.024$) between the predictor and the dependent variable, with only 0.1% of the variance explained. The ANOVA results show that the regression model is not statistically significant in predicting the dependent variable, as indicated by the non-significant F-value ($p = 0.792$). The Coefficients table further confirms the lack of significance, with a non-significant p-value ($p = 0.792$) for the predictor variable. Overall, these findings suggest that user experiences and review do not have a meaningful impact on the behavior or characteristics of Millennials and Post-Millennials in this analysis. Hence, the proposed hypothesis "*H5: The role of online reviews and ratings in influencing purchase decisions varies between Millennials and Post-Millennials*" is rejected.

10. IMPLICATIONS

To bridge the gaps in online purchase behavior between Millennials and Post-Millennials, businesses should consider the following elaborate suggestions. Firstly, personalization is crucial—utilize data analytics to deliver tailored recommendations and product suggestions based on individual preferences and browsing history. Incorporate user-generated content and social proof by encouraging customers to leave reviews and ratings, highlighting authentic experiences that build trust. Optimize mobile experiences with responsive design and intuitive navigation, catering to the significant use of smartphones for online shopping. Maintain a strong social media presence, regularly sharing engaging content and collaborating with influencers who resonate with Millennials and Post-Millennials. Offer secure and flexible payment options to instil confidence and convenience. Implement social sharing and referral programs to encourage word-of-mouth recommendations. Provide seamless customer support through various channels, addressing inquiries promptly and ensuring a positive post-purchase experience. By embracing these suggestions, businesses can create personalized, trustworthy, and convenient online shopping experiences that bridge the gaps between Millennials and

Post-Millennials, driving their online purchase behavior and fostering long-term engagement.

11. SUMMARY

This study has shed light on the gaps and differences in online purchase behavior between Millennials and Post-Millennials. The findings emphasize the need for businesses to understand and cater to the preferences and characteristics of these distinct generational groups. By implementing personalized experiences, leveraging user-generated content and social proof, optimizing mobile experiences, maintaining a strong social media presence, offering secure payment options, collaborating with influencers, enabling social sharing and referral programs, and providing seamless customer support, businesses can bridge these gaps and effectively engage Millennials and Post-Millennials in online shopping. These strategies, rooted in the analysis of the research data, provide valuable insights and actionable implications for businesses seeking to navigate the evolving digital landscape and tap into the vast potential of these generations as online consumers. By embracing these recommendations, businesses can create positive online shopping experiences, foster brand loyalty, and drive the desired online purchase behavior among Millennials and Post-Millennials.

12. FUTURE RESEARCH

Several avenues can be explored to deepen our understanding of the online purchase behavior of Millennials and Post-Millennials. Longitudinal studies can track changes over time, cross-cultural comparisons can uncover cultural influences, and investigations into emerging technologies like VR and AR can shed light on their impact. Ethical considerations surrounding privacy and sustainability, emotional and psychological factors, integration of offline and online channels, gender differences, and factors affecting consumer trust and loyalty are also promising areas of exploration. By delving into these subjects, researchers can contribute valuable insights that enable businesses to effectively engage Millennials and Post-Millennials and meet their evolving online shopping needs and expectations.

References

1. Alalwan, A. A., Rana, N. P., & Dwivedi, Y. K. (2017). The impact of social media marketing on online shopping behavior: A conceptual framework and empirical investigation. *International Journal of Information Management*, 37(6), 659-675.
2. Bhatnagar, A., & Ghose, S. (2004). Segmenting consumers based on the benefits and risks of Internet shopping. *Journal of Business Research*, 57(12), 1352–1360. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0148-2963\(03](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0148-2963(03)
3. Brengman, M., Geuens, M., Weijters, B., Smith, S., & Swinyard, W. (2005). Segmenting Internet shoppers based on their Web-usage-related lifestyle: A cross-cultural validation. *Journal of Business Research*, 58(1), 79–88. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0148-2963\(02](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0148-2963(02)
4. Brosdahl, D. J. C., & Carpenter, J. M. (2011). Shopping orientations of US males: A generational cohort comparison. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 18(6), 548–554. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2011.07.005>

5. Carpenter, J., Moore, M., Doherty, A., & Alexander, N. (2012). Acculturation to the global consumer culture: A generational cohort comparison. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 20(5), 411–4
6. Chang, H. H., Wang, Y. H., & Yang, W. Y. (2009). The impact of e-service quality, customer satisfaction and loyalty on e-marketing: Moderating effect of perceived value. *Total Quality Management and Business Excellence*, 20(4), 423–443. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14783360902781923>
7. Cheema, R., Rizwan, M., & Rizwan, M. (2018). Factors influencing purchase intentions of millennials in online shopping: A trust-based perspective. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 42, 101-110.
8. Chiu, C. M., Chang, C. C., Cheng, H. L., & Fang, Y. H. (2015). Determinants of customer repurchase intention in online shopping: A trust-based perspective. *Online Information Review*, 39(4), 761-784.
9. Du, R., Hu, Y., & Damangir, S. (2019). Mediating role of perceived risk in the relationship between trust, perceived usefulness, and perceived ease of use with online purchase intention: A study of millennials and post-millennials. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 48, 101853.
10. Guzmán-Parra, I., Hernández-Ortega, B., & Llorens-Monzonis, A. (2021). The role of social media in shaping online purchase intentions: A comparison between millennials and generation z. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 59, 102443.
11. Jain, V., & Bansal, S. (2019). Determinants of online shopping behavior among millennials: A study of Indian consumers. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 48, 101854. [doi:10.1016/j.jretconser.2019.01.008](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2019.01.008)
12. Koksál, M. (2019). Differences among baby boomers, generation X, millennials, and generation Z wine consumers in Lebanon: Some perspective.
13. Koksál, M. (2019). Differences among baby boomers, generation X, millennials, and generation Z wine consumers in Lebanon: Some perspective. *International Journal of Wine Business Research*, 31 (3), 456–472 DOI:10.1108/IJWBR-09-2018-0047
14. Kolnhofer, D. A., Reicher, R. Z., & Szeghegyi, A. (2017). The X and Y generations' characteristics comparison. *Acta Polytechnica Hungarica*, 14(8), 107–125. <https://doi.org/10.12700/APH.14.8.2017.8.6>
15. Kwak, S., Lee, S., & Kim, M. (2020). The impact of personalization and social influence on online shopping behavior of millennials: A conceptual framework and empirical investigation. *International Journal of Information Management*,
16. Laroche, M., Habibi, M. R., & Richard, M. O. (2019). The influence of social media and online reviews on online purchase intention: A study of millennials and post-millennials. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 97, 1755-1767.
17. Lee, S., Kwon, M., & Lee, J. (2019). Differences in online purchase behavior between millennials and baby boomers: A focus on perceived risk, trust, and convenience. *Internet Research*, 29(2), 307-328.
18. Lo, A., King, B., & Mackenzie, M. (2020). Segmenting Chinese millennial restaurant customers: a lifestyle and health and environmental consciousness approach. *Journal of China Tourism Research*, 16(2), 183–213. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19388160.2019.1604281>
19. Moreno, F.M., Lafuente, J.G., Carreon, F. & Moreno, S. (2017). The characterization of millennials and their buying behaviour. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, Vol 9 (5).
20. Rahman, M.A., Islam, M.A., Esha, B.H., Sultana, N., & Chakravorty, S. (2018). Consumer buying behaviour towards online shopping: an empirical study on Dhaka City, Bangladesh. *Congent Business and Management*, 5(1), 1-22.

20. Shaikh, A. (2020). Effective factors in changing the buying behaviour of consumer due to Covid-19. *Studies in Indian Place Names*, 40 68, 408–414 <https://www.bmij.org/index.php/1/article/view/1819>
21. Shams, G., Rehman, M., Samad, S., & Oikarinen, E. (2020). Exploring customer's mobile banking experiences and expectations among generations X, Y and Z. *Journal of Financial Services Marketing*, 25(1–2), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41264-020-00071-z>
22. Shaw, R., Kim, Y., & Hua, J. (2020). Governance, technology and citizen behaviour in pandemic: Lessons from COVID- 19 in East Asia. *Progress in Disaster Science*, 2020 , 100090. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pdisas.2020.100090>
23. Sladek, S., & Grabinger. (2014). Gen Z: The first generation of the 21st Century has arrived xyzuniversity. In *Next Generation Intelligence* (pp. 1–16).
24. Slater, S. F., & Narver, J. (2000). Intelligence generation and superior customer value. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 28(1), 120–127. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1177/0092070300281011>
25. Smith, K. (2011). Longitudinal study of digital marketing strategies targeting Millennials. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 29(2), 86-92.
26. [26] Wahyuningsih et al., *Cogent Business & Management* (2022), 9: 2105585 <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2022.2105585>
27. Wen-Chuah, S. H., Marimuthu, M., Kandampully, J., & Bilgihan, A. (2017). What drives Gen Y loyalty? Understanding the mediated moderating roles of switching costs and alternative attractiveness in the value-satisfaction-loyalty chain. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 36(July2016), 124–136. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2017.01.0102017.01.010>
28. Williams, K. C., & Page, R. (2011). Marketing to the Generations. *Journal of Behavioural Studies in Business*, 3(1), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0965254X.2017.12911730049>
29. Wu, T., & Lin, C. (2017). Predicting the effects of eWOM and online brand messaging: Source trust, bandwagon effect and innovation adoption factors. *Telematics and Informatics*, 34(2), 470–480. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2016.08.00153>, 102175.